

OPERATING PERIODS

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the modern nurse, in addition to knowing how to perform medical procedures, must also be able to identify the patient's existing and potential mental and social problems caused by the disease and direct all efforts in society to eliminate these problems. She must also master the art of communicating with the patient in such a way that she can help the patient escape the cycle of illness with her sweet words and gentle treatment. This article discusses the rules of ethics and law.

Keywords: Operation, antiseptics, surgery, diagnostics, anesthesia.

and organs for therapeutic or diagnostic purposes .

For many years, the word "surgery" has been associated with excruciating pain or the risk of death. Surgery before antiseptics was characterized by an anatomical orientation, in which the secrets of anesthesia, blood transfusion, and prevention of wound infection remained unknown.

Nowadays, surgical risks have been eliminated, and surgery has taken a physiological direction. This is achieved through a comprehensive examination of patients in the preoperative period, intensive observation of patients during the operation and postoperative periods. In modern surgery, the successful course of the operation is ensured by a sufficient reduction in pain perception.

Nowadays, all the conditions are sufficient for the surgeon to accurately assess the condition of organs and tissues, eliminate the pathological changes found in a timely and flawless manner, and, as a result, make operations effective.

Surgical operations are usually performed for therapeutic purposes, but there are also operations performed for diagnostic purposes. Diagnostic operations include taking biopsies, punctures of the abdominal, pleural, joint cavities, epidural puncture , etc. , endoscopic examinations (cystoscopy, bronchoscopy, esophagoscopy, gastroscopy, thoracoscopy, laparoscopy, etc.), angiography and cardiac catheterization, diagnostic thoracotomy and laparotomies.

- Radical operations

Radical operations are those in which the affected organ or tissue is cut out or removed (appendectomy, stomach resection), and this does not lead to a recurrence of the disease. Radical operations are extended (extended) and combined (in the case of a malignant tumor of the stomach that has grown into surrounding organs, the spleen, part of the liver and lymph nodes are removed at the same time).

- Palliative surgeries

Palliative operations do not eliminate the cause of the disease, but only alleviate the patient's condition. For example, if a malignant tumor has blocked the large intestine and its radical removal is not possible, a loop of intestine is removed to the anterior abdominal wall. In this case, the intestinal tumor is not removed, but the intestinal obstruction is eliminated and an artificial external intestinal fistula is created.

Urgent (non - urgent or emergency) operations

Undelayable (untimely) Emergency operations are performed within the first two hours after the patient is admitted to the hospital and the diagnosis is made (acute appendicitis, perforation of a stomach ulcer, strangulated hernia, acute intestinal obstruction). In some cases (acute bleeding, tracheostomy), operations may have to be performed within the next few minutes, depending on vital indications .

- Urgent operations

Urgent operations are performed in the first days after the patient is admitted to the hospital, since the patient's condition may reach a level that makes surgery impossible due to the rapid progression of the process (malignant tumors, external intestinal fistulas, severe congenital heart defects).

- Scheduled operations

Scheduled surgeries can be performed at any time, and preparation for the surgery can last a day or two, or even weeks if necessary.

In most cases, operations are performed in one stage (appendectomy, gastric resection, lobectomy, plasty of the interventricular septal defect). If the patient's condition is serious, the volume of the operation is large and risky, then in such cases the operation can be performed in several stages. For example, if the size of the inflammatory infiltrate in a periappendicular abscess is large, only the operation to open and drain the purulent cavity is performed, and appendectomy is performed several months after the inflammatory processes have resolved.

Examples of multi-stage surgeries include skin grafting, Filatov's method of migrating pouching, esophageal bypass grafting with a small intestinal loop in front of the sternum, or staged removal of large hemangiomas.

Indications for operations may be:

1. Necessary for life.
2. Absolute.
3. Relative.

Absolute indications are given in cases where surgery is the only treatment for this disease.

Relative indications are given when there are other treatment options available, although they are less effective. Relative indications are often used in elective surgeries, when it is possible to temporarily abandon the operation without significant harm to the patient's health. In one disease, the indication for surgery can be either vital, absolute, or relative. For example, in complicated duodenal ulcer, the indication for surgery can be vital (in case of profuse bleeding, when

conservative hemostatic treatment is ineffective), or absolute (in case of stenosis), or relative (in cases where no conservative treatment measures have been taken).

When prescribing an operation, it is necessary to take into account not only the consequences of the disease, but also the capabilities of the operating surgeon, the level of availability of the operating room (equipment and equipment). If the surgeon is not confident in the success of the operation he is performing, he should refuse the operation, because surgery is not a sport, and a person is not an object of experimentation. The large number of operations performed does not mean that the surgeon has exceeded his knowledge. In addition to assisting the surgeon, it is necessary to carefully observe the operations performed by qualified surgeons and improve their skills.

To prevent unnecessary surgeries, the surgeon must thoroughly familiarize himself with the patients, plan the operation, and create a preoperative plan. The preoperative plan should reflect the following:

1. Justification of the diagnosis.
2. Instructions for surgery (pokazaniya k operatsii).
3. Plan of the operation being performed (operation plan).
4. Type of anesthesia (type of anesthesia).

Surgical operation is a complex process, in which three main stages are distinguished:

1. Preoperative period and patients
for surgery .
2. Direct surgical operation.
3. Patients in the postoperative period
intensive monitoring and care of the condition .

Ensuring all of the above steps is the key to the success of the operation.

- Preoperative period

The preoperative period includes the period from the time patients are admitted to the hospital or outpatient clinic until the start of the operation. The preoperative period can be divided into two stages:

- 1) Determining the diagnosis .
- 2) preparation for surgery .

At the first stage, the diagnosis of the disease is established, the condition of all organs and systems is examined, and indications for surgery are determined.

In the second stage, patients are prepared for surgery.

, measures are taken to prevent postoperative complications and improve the functional state of the organs. Extensive, radical surgeries require more preparation than palliative surgeries.

The following periods are distinguished in preparation for planned operations:

1. Remote preoperative period (otdalenn iy y preoperative period) .
2. The immediate preoperative period (immediate preoperative period .
3. Immediate preoperative period (neposredstvenn iy preoperatsionn iy y period) .

For example, in the case of goiter or heart defects, sanatorium treatment is recommended in the preoperative period, and cleft palates and carious teeth are repaired.

In the immediate preoperative period (7-15 days), attention is paid to the state of somatic systems, and in the immediate preoperative period, sanitary and hygienic procedures are performed, including emptying the bladder and rectum.

A distinction is made between immediate preoperative and general (specific) measures. Immediate preoperative measures are distinguished by their uniformity and necessity, and include taking a hygienic bath, shaving, cleansing enemas, and emptying the bladder.

General (specific) measures differ in that they are performed before certain operations, for example, emptying the stomach in case of pyloroduodenal stenosis, performing a siphon enema before colon surgery , and sanitizing the bronchi in case of purulent lung diseases.

Preoperative preparation also includes the following :

- 1) The nervous condition of the patients .
- 2) general somatic condition.
3. by studying local processes
will improve .

Preparation of the patients nervous system includes:

1. Calming patients.
2. Fight insomnia.
3. It is necessary to obtain the personal consent of the patients for the operation, and if the patient is a child, the consent of the parents must be obtained.

Preparation of the general somatic condition of patients includes:

1. Changes in the circulatory system
elimination .
2. Changes in the respiratory system
elimination .
3. Elimination of anemia.
4. Prevention of thrombosis and embolism.
5. Preparing the digestive system.
6. Preparation of the genitourinary tract.

Local somatic preparation of patients includes:

1. Check the operating area for any changes.
check .
2. Order a bath and change clothes.
3. Shaving and cleaning the hair in the surgical area.

- The surgical operation is divided into several stages:

1. Lay the patient on the operating table.
2. Preparation of the operating area.
3. Anesthesia.
4. Choosing an operative path (access).
5. Perform the operation.
6. End of operation.

- The position of patients on the operating table

1. Supine position (polozhenie na spine).
2. Trendelenburg position.
3. Lateral position.
4. Gynecological condition.
5. Prone position (prone position) .
6. The patient's semi-sitting position: during operations on the posterior cranial cavity (polusidyachee polozhenie bol ь nogo : pri operatsikh na zadney cherepnoy yamke).

The area where the operation will be performed is called the operating field. After the skin is prepared, the operating field is covered with drapes , leaving only the incision open. Large and small drapes, towels, and napkins are used to cover the operating field .

In minor, outpatient surgeries, local anesthesia is used to numb the nerve endings in a specific area.

In surgeries performed under anesthesia, the surgical field is prepared after anesthesia is administered, as the patient may compromise the sterility of the surgical field during the period of anesthesia.

be convenient for reaching the pathological focus and facilitate the operation. The operative route should be anatomically correct and cause minimal tissue damage.

The postoperative period includes the period from the time the operation is completed until the patient regains his or her ability to work. The postoperative period is divided into three phases:

1. Early phase – postoperative

includes the first 3-5 days.

2. Late phase – 2-3 days after surgery

includes the week .

3. The distant phase – includes the period until patients regain their ability to work.

Surgery is both a physical and psychological trauma for patients. In the postoperative period, regenerative and reparative processes occur that are not observed in a healthy body. The course of the postoperative period can be 1) smooth or normal and 2) complicated. In the first case, a slightly expressed reaction of the body (moderately expressed reaction of the body), and in the second case, a sharply expressed (hyperergic or anergic) state of the body to the surgical trauma is observed , which can lead to sharp functional changes in the body and, as a result, complications.

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